

Synthesis and characterization of diopside by sol-gel combustion method by using L-alanine as a fuel for biomedical applications

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Abstract : Bioceramic calcium silicates have evolved as a potential biomaterial for artificial bone and dental root implants due to its excellent bioactivity and improved mechanical strength hence in the present work we aimed to convert the bio-waste into a useful biomaterial. In this study diopside ($\text{CaMgSi}_2\text{O}_6$) has been successfully prepared by sol-gel combustion method by using L-alanine as a fuel, nitrate ions as an oxidiser and egg shell (chicken) as a calcium source. Optimization of calcination temperature resulted in a well crystalline diopside powders with high phase purity. Synthesized powders were characterized by powder-XRD for phase identification, FT-IR spectroscopy for functional group analysis and scanning electron microscope for the measurement of particle size and surface morphology.

Keywords : Bioceramic, bioactivity, diopside, bio-waste, powder-XRD.

Introduction

A wide range of bioactive glass ceramics find high demand in biological applications ranging from bone implant to damaged hard tissue repair. Compositional as well as morphological properties play fundamental role in the bioactivity of bioceramics and the field like Dentistry has advanced by using bioceramics as dental fillers which matches to the patient's natural teeth in appearance as well as in functions. Significant difference in the composition also leads to improved compressive strength and mechanical stability of glass ceramics over calcium phosphate ceramics. Porous nature provides path for blood supply to the ingrown connective tissues and facilitates the mechanical strength by making it capable of withstanding more stress¹.

Highly focused research is going on bioactive glass ceramics which can be applied as a potential candidate for drug delivery and biomedical applications. It is found that silica based biomaterials have the ability to release silicate ions at a definite concentration which promotes osteoblasts growth and proliferation². Silicon plays a significant role in the nucleation and growth mechanism of the apatite like layer on bioactive ceramic surface^{3,4}. Different silicate bioceramics like Diopside, Akermanite, Pseudowollastonite, Forsterite and Protoenstatite was syn-

thesized by solid solution method and analyzed for its apatite precipitation ability which shows that less magnesium elution can cause more apatite precipitation and presence of magnesium ions *in vivo* has possibilities to improve biocompatibility⁵. *In vitro* bioactivity studies of glass ceramics results in the formation of apatite layer on the scaffold surface when it is immersed in simulated body fluid^{6,7}.

Several conventional methods have been employed for the synthesis of pure diopside. Nanodiopside synthesized by sol-gel method was used as a potential candidate in biomedical applications⁸. Diopside prepared by sintering method was analysed for cell toxicity and found to possess no cell toxicity⁹. Later, metal alkoxide and metal salts were used to synthesize diopside by co-precipitation process and the *in vitro* bioactivity of the pure phase was evaluated⁶. Single phasic diopside was also prepared by hydrothermal method at high temperature¹⁰. In this study we have attempted a low temperature synthesis of diopside by energy efficient and cost effective sol-gel combustion method.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Tetraethyl ortho silicate (98%, Acros Organics), mag-

nesium nitrate purified LR (99.0% SDFCL), chicken egg shell, L-alanine CHR (99.0%, SDFCL), concentrated nitric acid LR (69–72%, SDFCL), ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) LR (98.0%, SDFCL), Eriochrome black-T AR (99%, SDFCL), ammonia solution extrapure AR (25%, SRL), ammonium chloride GR (98.8%, Merck).

Extraction of calcium from egg shell and estimation of calcium ions by EDTA titration :

The shells were removed from boiled chicken eggs and dried completely in hot air oven for 2 h which were then crushed to fine powder by using mortar and pestle. To prepare 1 M calcium ion solution, 10 g of egg shell powder was dissolved in 15 ml conc. HNO_3 and the solution was allowed to stand for 1 h for the completion of reaction. The solution was filtered by using Wattmann's 41 filter paper and the filtrate was collected in the standard flask and un-reacted proteins were separated and discarded. The filtrate collected in a standard flask was made up to 100 ml with double distilled water and used as a stock solution for further experiments.

The concentration of calcium ions was estimated by EDTA titration. From the stock solution 20 ml of the egg shell solution was pipetted out into a conical flask and 10 ml of ammonia buffer and 3–4 drops of Eriochrome black-T indicator was added. Resulting mixture was stirred vigorously for thorough mixing and then it was titrated against the standardized EDTA solution taken in burette, the colour change from wine red to steel blue indicates the end point. Concentration of calcium ion present in the egg shell solution was found to be 0.98 M.

Synthesis of diopside :

Stock solution of magnesium nitrate and L-alanine was prepared separately in the 100 ml standard flask. 20 ml egg shell solution, 20 ml magnesium nitrate solution, 40 ml of L-alanine (fuel) solution and 9 ml TEOS (tetraethyl ortho silicate) were pipetted out in to a beaker and mixed thoroughly by using a magnetic stirrer. 5 ml nitric acid was added to the mixture to maintain the pH at 1 and the resultant solution was stirred on the magnetic stirrer for 4 h at room temperature. The resultant solution was heated at 50 °C and stirred for 1 h and then kept for overnight ageing. The dense transparent gel formed was dried in hot air oven at 150 °C for 4 h. The dried gel was decomposed in a preheated muffle furnace for 2 h at 400 °C in

the presence of air to facilitate the combustion of L-alanine by the oxidant. The precursor was grinded to fine powder by using mortar and pestle and calcined at 850 °C for 6 h. The calcined product was characterized by FT-IR spectroscopy, powder-XRD and scanning electron microscopy techniques.

Characterization of diopside :

Phase identification of the synthesized diopside was studied by using X-ray diffractometer (Bruker, D8 Advance, Germany), using $\text{CuK}\alpha$, Ni filtered radiation. Functional groups present in the synthesized diopside were examined by FT-IR spectrophotometer (IR Affinity-1, Shimadzu). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM-CARL ZEISS, Model no. Sigma VP) was used for the morphological analysis.

Results and discussion

Nitric acid plays a major role in hydrolysis of TEOS into silanol and ethyl alcohol. Calcium nitrate and magnesium nitrate provides nitrate ions for combustion. The silanol reacts with calcium ions and magnesium ions to form a complex and ethyl alcohol with L-alanine (fuel) to undergo poly condensation reaction resulting in the formation of dense gel. Combustion reaction includes successive exothermic chemical reaction between the gel and nitrate ions (oxidizing agent) followed by the production of heat to raise the internal temperature of the reaction mixture to aid the phase formation. Combustion also helps in evolution of large amount of gases (NH_3 , H_2O and CO_2) which help to disperse the heat preventing oxides from sintering¹¹. The brown colour of the precursor indicates the presence of carbonaceous and nitrate groups which were removed by further thermal treatment by calcinating at 850 °C for 6 h to form a grey crystalline powder indicating total removal of carbonaceous and nitrate groups.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) :

Fig. 1 shows FT-IR spectrum of diopside sample calcined at 850 °C for 6 h in which the bending modes of O-Ca-O bonds were observed at 395 to 415 cm^{-1} , O-Mg-O bending modes at 474 to 515 cm^{-1} , the O-Si-O bending modes were observed in the range of 636 to 677 cm^{-1} while the stretching modes of Si-O bonds were observed between 870 to 1070 cm^{-1} . The moisture band was observed in the range of 3000–4000 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectra of diopside calcined at 850 °C.

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of diopside calcined at 850 °C.

Fig. 3. SEM images of porous diopside.

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) :

Purity of the bioceramics plays a significant role in bioactivity. The phase examination of diopside was carried out by powder X-ray diffractometer. XRD pattern

(Fig. 2) reveals the formation of single phasic diopside with monoclinic crystal system confirmed with JCPDS data card no. 96-100-0008. The pattern is indexed to the same and the lattice parameters calculated from the powder XRD was found to be $a = 9.73992 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 8.91935 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.24995 \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 105.884$.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) :

Surface morphology influences the bioactivity of the ceramic biomaterials. Porosity plays a vital role in bone growth by influencing migration, proliferation and differentiation of the cells. SEM images of the calcined diopside powder shows that particles are highly agglomerated (Fig. 3a) and possesses irregular morphology (Fig. 3b) with the particle size in the range of 300–500 nm. The porous nature of the particles is due to the evolution of gasses like NH_3 , H_2O and CO_2 during combustion process.

Conclusion

Synthesis of pure crystalline diopside ($\text{CaMgSi}_2\text{O}_6$) was carried out by energy efficient sol-gel combustion method by using L-alanine as a fuel for the first time. The work demonstrates the conversion of bio-waste like chicken egg shell into a useful bioceramic. In addition the calci-

nations temperature is brought down to 850 °C which is comparatively very less when compared with other methods hence this method of preparation will be an energy efficient process.

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